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IAS Academic Corner - Case 2

Pan Labral Tear: An Underrecognized Cause of Shoulder Pain and Instability – A Case Report and Review of Literature

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Abstract

- ◆ Pan labral tears involve circumferential detachment of the superior, anterior, and posterior glenoid labrum.
- ◆ Clinical findings may be disproportionate to MRI findings, making diagnosis challenging.
- ◆ Positive apprehension and O'Brien's tests should raise suspicion of extensive labral pathology.
- ◆ Preoperative MRI may underestimate the true extent of labral injury.
- ◆ Diagnostic arthroscopy remains the gold standard for identifying pan labral lesions.
- ◆ Successful treatment requires comprehensive arthroscopic repair using multiple suture anchors.

Case Summary and Review of Literature

Pan labral tears are circumferential injuries involving the superior, anterior, and posterior glenoid labrum. Although traditionally considered uncommon, increasing arthroscopic experience has demonstrated that these lesions may be more prevalent than previously recognized. Diagnosis remains challenging because clinical findings are often nonspecific and preoperative imaging may fail to identify the full extent of the injury.

A 38-year-old right-hand dominant male presented with pain and restricted movement of his right shoulder following a fall onto the affected shoulder one month earlier. He reported a previous injury to the same shoulder four years prior but had remained asymptomatic thereafter. The patient was a non-athlete and complained of persistent difficulty in shoulder abduction following the recent trauma.

Initial radiographs showed no evidence of fracture or dislocation. Despite one month of conservative treatment, including analgesics and activity modification, he continued to experience pain and functional limitation.

Clinical examination revealed restricted active shoulder motion. Active abduction was limited to 80°, while passive abduction improved to 140°. Active external rotation was 30° and passive external rotation 40°. Active and passive internal rotation measured 30° and 50°, respectively. The apprehension test was positive, indicating shoulder instability, while O'Brien's test was also positive, suggesting associated superior labral pathology.

MRI evaluation demonstrated labral abnormalities; however, the circumferential extent of the lesion was not clearly appreciated preoperatively. In view of persistent symptoms and clinical suspicion of instability, diagnostic shoulder arthroscopy was undertaken.

Arthroscopic evaluation revealed a circumferential tear involving the superior, anterior, and posterior labrum, consistent with a pan labral lesion. A concomitant SLAP lesion was identified. Arthroscopic repair was performed using multiple suture anchors placed sequentially to restore labral integrity and shoulder stability. Stable fixation was achieved, and the patient subsequently underwent a structured rehabilitation program.

Pan labral tears are increasingly recognized in patients presenting with shoulder instability. Owens et al. reported that approximately 28.8% of labral repairs involve more than one functional area of the labrum, suggesting that complex labral pathology is not uncommon. Tokish et al. reported circumferential lesions involving the superior, anterior, and posterior labrum in approximately 6.5% of arthroscopic labral repairs.

One of the greatest challenges in managing pan labral tears is accurate diagnosis. Clinical symptoms may be nonspecific, and MRI has demonstrated poor sensitivity for identifying circumferential labral lesions. Consequently, detailed history-taking and meticulous physical examination remain essential. Diagnostic arthroscopy continues to be the gold standard for identifying the full extent of injury.

Ricchetti et al. demonstrated favorable outcomes following arthroscopic repair of circumferential labral tears, although recurrent instability, postoperative stiffness, and revision surgery have been reported. The present case highlights the importance of maintaining a high index of suspicion in patients with persistent symptoms after shoulder trauma, particularly when imaging findings do not correlate with clinical examination.

In conclusion, pan labral tears are likely underrecognized injuries that require careful clinical assessment and thorough arthroscopic evaluation. Preoperative MRI may be misleading, and surgeons should be prepared for extensive labral repair requiring multiple suture anchors.

Figure Legends

Figure 1

Preoperative MRI of the right shoulder.

(A) Axial section demonstrating labral pathology.

(B) Coronal section demonstrating superior labral involvement.

The circumferential extent of the lesion was not fully appreciated on preoperative imaging.

Figure 2

A) Arthroscopic findings and repair of pan labral tear.

B) Circumferential detachment involving the Superior, Anterior, and Posterior Labrum.

(A) Arthroscopic repair using multiple suture anchors restoring labral continuity and shoulder stability- Anterior Labrum

(B) Arthroscopic repair using multiple suture anchors Posterior Labrum

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